

EXPERIENCE IN THE USE OF THE MIXTURE IN CHILDREN OF THE FIRST YEAR OF LIFE

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Summary: Adapted milk formulas are used when feeding children under 1 year old, with a lack or absence of mother's milk. This article presents the results of a study of the effectiveness of the milk formula, which was studied on 40 patients aged from 1 month to 1 year with various pathologies who applied to the family clinic No. 2 of the city of Samarkand.

Keywords: breast milk, adapted milk mixture, hemoglobin, iron deficiency anemia, atopic dermatitis.

Relevance. Currently, pediatricians around the world have recognized that the ideal food for children in the first year of life is mother's milk. However, most often you have to deal with the problem of a lack of mother's milk or its complete absence. In this regard, the development of new mixtures and technologies for feeding newborns and infants seems to be an urgent task.

The "Malyutka" formula is a full-fledged adapted milk formula for feeding children from birth to the 1st year of life with a lack or absence of breast milk in the mother. It contains demineralized whey proteins, a mixture of vegetable and animal fats with a predominance of vegetable oils and contains the optimal amount of omega 6 and omega 3 polyunsaturated fatty acids, lactose, maltodextrin, the whole complex of essential microelements (selenium, iodine, iron, manganese, copper, zinc), a balanced composition of biologically active substances (choline, inositol, L-carnitine).

Purpose of the study. Analysis of the effectiveness of the use of mixtures of the budget class in children who are bottle-fed.

Material and methods. The study included 40 children, of which 20 children from 1 to 6 months old received the mixture "Malyutka1" and 20 children from 6 months to 1 year old received the mixture "Malyutka2".

The structure of morbidity in children who received the formula "Baby": The main disease is perinatal CNS damage 20%, SARS - 18%, acute bronchitis 12%, pneumonia 20%, anemia 30%; concomitant disease - rickets 1-2 st 10%, acquired malnutrition 1-2 st 10%, atopic dermatitis 60%, enterocolitis 4%.

All the children observed by us were bottle-fed (due to the lack of milk from the mother). Children with various pathologies were admitted to the family polyclinic No. 2 (the percentage is given above). The largest number (90%) were children with iron deficiency anemia. In the clinical picture in children of the neonatal period, one or more concomitant diseases dominated, such as rickets of 1-2 degrees (10%), malnutrition of 1-2 degrees (10%), manifestation of atopic dermatitis (60%).

Research results and discussion. The period of adaptation to this mixture in all children was uneventful. None of the children had allergic reactions. The state of health of children on the background of receiving the mixture "Malyutka" did not deteriorate, the dynamics of weight and growth indicators were within the age norm. Colic, regurgitation, constipation were not observed. In 5 children with mild manifestations of atopic dermatitis, taking the

"Malyutka" mixture did not cause an increase in allergic manifestations on the skin. Clinical analyzes of blood and urine before and after formula feeding remained within the age norm. The level of hemoglobin in the dynamics slightly increased and amounted to 114 g/l at the end of the observation, while before the mixture was obtained, its value was 90 g/l.

Thus, the formula "Malyutka" is a full-fledged milk formula for feeding children of the 1st year of life. The results of the studies conducted allow us to speak with confidence about the good tolerability of the mixture by children, from the neonatal period to the first year of life, and the absence of any side effects. The mixture can be recommended for mixed or artificial feeding of children from birth to 1 year with a lack or absence of mother's milk.

Conclusion. Mixtures produced by "Malyutka" are a complete milk formula for feeding both healthy and sick children. The results of the studies carried out allow us to talk about the good tolerance of the mixture by children without the absence of side effects. Mixtures can be recommended for mixed and artificial feeding of young children with a lack or absence of mother's milk.

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